

Towards a Holistic Data-Driven Framework for Multi-Domain Threat Assessment and Situational Awareness in Maritime Critical Infrastructure

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Abstract—Maritime critical infrastructures (MCI) such as ports, bridges or liquefied natural gas (LNG) terminals are key nodes in global supply chains and energy provision. They are increasingly exposed to complex, interdependent threats from the domains water, air and cyber, including cyberattacks, global navigation satellite system (GNSS) interference, spoofed communication protocols, uncooperative drones and small vessels. Existing multi-sensor systems typically provide object detection but offer only limited assessment of the actual threat potential and lack structured interfaces to public authorities. This paper presents the conceptual framework for the DIEB project (Data-Driven Identification and Evaluation of Threats on Maritime Infrastructure), which aims to close this capability gap for MCI operators by developing a data-driven security situation picture and an explainable, AI-supported threat analysis. Core components of the proposed system are (i) a real-time decision support and alerting system, (ii) automated threat assessment based on Big Data analytics and artificial intelligence, and (iii) a data-sovereign system architecture integrating stationary and mobile sensor platforms. Using a data platform that fuses AIS, ADS-L, radar, visual, thermal and IT-security data, the DIEB concept shall enable operators to proactively identify relevant threats in each domain (water, air, cyber), evaluate their criticality, and trigger targeted, authority-driven response chains. The concept is designed to be modular and scalable to other MCI such as offshore wind farms, underwater cables and pipelines.

Index Terms—Maritime security, critical infrastructure, real-time situational awareness, automated threat assessment, artificial intelligence, decision support system, mobile sensor platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

MARITIME critical infrastructures (MCI), such as ports and liquefied natural gas (LNG) terminals, are central nodes of the global economy and energy supply chains [1], [2]. Around 90% of global trade is handled by sea, and the amount of LNG imports just increased to about 14% of all German natural gas imports. Which shows the growing significance in the goal of diversifying the national energy supply [3].

Due to the central role, coastal location and strong dependence on digital information systems, MCI are attractive targets for criminal and terrorist attacks from different domains [2, p. 14], [4].

Recent incidents demonstrate a broad and growing threat spectrum. Cyberattacks against shipping companies have caused hundreds of millions of dollars in damage [5], while jamming and spoofing increasingly manipulate navigation and communication processes [6], [7]. At the same time, armed,

spying or signal-jamming drones [8]–[10], shadow fleets [11], [12] and outdated vessels with vulnerable digital systems pose additional risks [13]–[15]. Given the complexity and interdependence of these threats, it is essential to detect, assess and address hazards at an early stage. Due to growing interdependence relying solely on human threat assessment is increasingly prone to error due to information overload [16].

According to the ISPS Code [17], the responsibility for the security of MCI lies with the operators, while active defensive measures are reserved for public authorities. Modern security systems must therefore be able to recognize threats proactively, assess them in real time and provide targeted information to relevant authorities [18]. Data-driven approaches using Big Data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI) and advanced networking offer significant potential to detect anomalous behaviour, create real-time situational pictures and support decision makers [19].

The project DIEB (Data-Driven Identification and Evaluation of Threats on Maritime Infrastructure) addresses this challenge using the LNG terminal in Wilhelmshaven as an exemplary application case [20]. Together, Niedersachsen Ports (NPorts), the Fraunhofer-Center für Maritime Logistik und Dienstleistungen (CML) and associated partners aim to develop and validate a modular framework that can be transferred to further MCI sites (see Acknowledgment section for consortium details).

II. RELATED WORK

The protection of maritime critical infrastructures against threats from air, water, and cyber domains requires sophisticated monitoring systems that integrate heterogeneous sensor data. This section provides an overview of existing approaches, identifies current capability gaps, and positions the DIEB project's contributions.

A. Maritime Surveillance Technologies

Modern maritime surveillance must combine the consideration of *cooperative* and *non-cooperative* vehicles. Cooperative vehicles use standardized communication protocols to transmit position and identity information, like AIS (Automatic Identification System) for ships and ADS-L (Automatic Dependent Surveillance - Light) for aircraft [21], [22].

Non-cooperative vehicles do not provide any such information. Therefore, their identification is essential for early detection of sabotage threats through for example unauthorized drones and shadow fleets. Radar systems, electro-optical (EO) and infrared (IR) cameras, acoustic sensors, satellite surveillance, and radio frequency monitoring provide the complementary detection capabilities for such cases [23], [24]. Multi-sensor fusion approaches integrate these heterogeneous data sources to overcome limitations of single-sensor systems and reduce blind spots [25], [26].

B. AI and Big Data Analytics in Maritime Security

Classical surveillance systems rely on fixed threshold values or manual image analysis, which proves insufficient for complex, multi-domain threat scenarios [27]. Modern approaches leverage Big Data analytics and artificial intelligence to process large volumes of sensor data in real-time [26], [28].

Machine learning methods enable automated pattern recognition for anomaly detection and threat analysis [25], [29]. Advanced software-based situational awareness systems provide visual decision support through graphical representation of warnings and automated alerts [22], [30].

C. Existing Maritime Security Projects

The relevance of this topic is evident in numerous research projects. MARLIN developed a networked sensor and situational awareness system for maritime infrastructures [25], [31]. VIGIMARE focused on collaboration between MCI operators and EU states through a Virtual Control Room with AI-based threat detection [31]. SeaSentry researched a land-based passive sensor network for ship movement analysis [32]. ARGUS combined satellite imagery with ship position data for automated monitoring of critical underwater infrastructure [33]. MSDF integrated commercial satellite data with military information into a situational picture [32]. The DIEB project differentiates itself through its focus on assessing threat potential and defining specific response chains, information requirements, and responsibilities compared to previous research.

D. Capability Gaps and Research Needs

Despite advances in multi-sensor systems and digital situational awareness platforms, several critical capability gaps remain from the perspective of maritime critical infrastructure operators and security authorities. Existing coastal and port surveillance solutions primarily focus on generating a consolidated traffic picture and on detecting objects of interest. However, they rarely provide an explicit, machine-supported assessment of the threat potential associated with observed behaviour, nor do they derive concrete response options, escalation paths and information requirements for different stakeholder groups. Threat assessment therefore remains largely manual, depends heavily on operator experience, and is difficult to reproduce or explain retroactively.

A second gap concerns the fragmentation of monitoring across domains. The correlation of weak signals across

domains is essential to detect hybrid attack patterns in which individually minor incidents (e.g. drone overflights, GNSS interference, anomalous AIS behaviour, cyber alerts) only reveal their relevance when considered jointly in space and time.

From a systems-engineering perspective, there is a lack of data-sovereign, vendor-independent architectures that allow operators to integrate heterogeneous sensor data into a unified, high-quality data basis while retaining control over sensitive information. Many commercial solutions are closed, difficult to extend and, by design, insufficiently prepared for real-time Big Data processing or future forensic analysis. This represents a threat to digital sovereignty and limits the ability of operators to adapt their security posture to evolving threat scenarios.

These capability gaps motivate the three core components of the DIEB project: (i) a real-time decision support and alerting system that aggregates multi-domain information, prioritizes events according to their threat potential and initiates predefined notification chains for operators and public authorities; (ii) automated threat assessment based on Big Data analytics and artificial intelligence, which can detect anomalous behaviour across water, air and cyber domains and assess its criticality in an explainable way; and (iii) a data-sovereign system architecture that flexibly integrates stationary and mobile sensor platforms, provides a consistent data basis for operations and forensics, and keeps MCI operators in control of sensitive security-relevant data.

III. CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY

The DIEB concept was developed using a structured, interview-based requirements process with key stakeholders from MCI operators, security authorities, and regulatory bodies. This section summarizes the methodology used to derive the system architecture, functional requirements, and representative security scenarios.

A. Stakeholder Requirements Gathering

Structured stakeholder requirements were determined on five expert interviews with nine representatives of the main maritime critical infrastructure stakeholder groups, including operative site management and security, civil traffic authorities, port security regulators, state-level police and intelligence, and specialized UAV-defence experts. For each group, a tailored questionnaire covered roles and mandates, typical threat scenarios in the air, water, and cyber domains, existing detection and escalation procedures, and information and data needs. The interview material was qualitatively analysed and consolidated into 55 system-level requirements, harmonized across stakeholders and grouped into thematic clusters such as situational awareness, decision support and alerting, data integration, human-machine interface, security and compliance, and system operation and organisation.

In addition to this requirement set, we derived representative security scenarios from the interview material to characterize the threat landscape and support later validation and evaluation. These scenarios, which span air, water, cyber and hybrid constellations, are described in detail in Section III-B.

Fig. 1. DIEB system architecture with acquisition, analysis, and communication layers supported by a central data platform

B. Security Scenario Definition

Building on the stakeholder input and interview analysis described in Section III-A, the DIEB project defines a set of canonical security scenarios that represent the predominant threat landscape for maritime critical infrastructures across the air, water and cyber domains. These scenarios were used to validate the completeness and consistency of the elicited requirements (scenario-based requirements engineering) and will guide the design and later evaluation of the DIEB demonstrator.

In the air domain, physical intrusion threats include unauthorized drone surveillance and potential UAV attacks on port facilities and LNG terminals. Relevant patterns are repetitive overflights of the same objects, slow “scanning” behaviour, or flights near critical zones without remote identification signals. The scenarios assume a multi-sensor detection approach combining radar, electro-optical and infrared cameras, acoustic arrays and radio-frequency monitoring to track both cooperative and non-cooperative UAVs, and to distinguish harmless amateur flights from targeted reconnaissance or attack profiles.

In the water domain, threats range from unauthorized intrusion of small or non-cooperative vessels into exclusion zones to deliberate collisions with critical transport infrastructure or terminals. For these scenarios, video surveillance, thermal imaging and maritime sensor data (AIS,

radar) are combined to detect vessels that behave atypically, for example by lingering near sensitive structures, deviating from expected routes or exhibiting implausible speed and manoeuvre profiles. AIS spoofing is addressed by cross-validating position reports with independent radar detections, while GNSS jamming and spoofing attacks affecting navigation integrity are identified through ground-based reference sensor validation.

In the cyber domain, the scenarios include attacks on the IT and OT of KRITIS operators that can degrade safety-critical processes or situational awareness, as well as social-engineering-driven insider threats. Here, DIEB does not replace existing cyber-security tools but assumes that relevant cyber events are provided via interfaces and represented in the integrated situation picture alongside physical events.

As already highlighted in Section II, the most critical situations are hybrid constellations in which temporally and spatially clustered minor events jointly indicate a sophisticated threat. The scenarios therefore explicitly require systematic correlation of air-, water- and cyber-domain incidents so that attacks designed to distract operators, degrade sensor performance or exploit situational blind spots can be recognized as a single, coordinated pattern.

IV. PROJECT APPROACH AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The DIEB project addresses these capability gaps by developing a data-driven security situational awareness system

with automated threat assessment and decision support. This section outlines the conceptual, layered system architecture and its central data-sovereign platform; a first prototype is being deployed at the LNG terminal in Wilhelmshaven, where scenario-based trials will provide empirical results on detection performance, false alarm rates and time-to-alert.

A. Overall System Architecture

The DIEB system follows a layered architecture as depicted in Figure 1, which consists of three functional layers connected by a central data platform. The acquisition layer handles data ingestion from heterogeneous sensor sources across the air, water, and cyber domains, transforming raw sensor data into a standardized object and event model. The data platform serves as a storage platform that holds extracted object and event features, computed risk metrics, and structured incident databases for forensic analysis. All data flows through this centralized data repository, enabling consistent data management and seamless integration between the processing layers. The analysis layer performs domain-specific and holistic threat assessment, deriving risk metrics, hazard categorizations, and action recommendations from the acquired data. Finally, the communication layer delivers the prepared information to users via a web-based human-machine interface (HMI) and API interfaces for integration with external systems. The key goal here is to provide humanly understandable AI methods for threat assessment that simplify transparent decision-making processes.

B. Central Data Platform Architecture

The central data platform combines storage for raw sensor data with curated, analytics-ready datasets. Gathered data from stationary and mobile platforms across the air, water, and cyber domains are ingested into a unified repository, where they are normalized into a consistent object and event model. On this basis, the system extracts and stores feature data (e.g., tracks, flight paths, security incidents), which are used by the analysis layer to compute threat assessments and risk scores, including aggregated danger indices and reaction time projections. A dedicated, incident database captures timestamps, involved assets, and response actions, providing a consistent foundation for both real-time operational decisions and later forensic or model-improvement analyses while preserving operator data sovereignty.

C. Multi-Domain Threat Detection

In line with the security scenarios described in Section III-B, multi-domain threat detection in DIEB is realized by applying domain-specific analytics modules on the shared data-streams.

In the water and air domains, analytics modules derive tracks and behaviour descriptors from fused sensor data (such as position, speed, heading changes or loitering patterns) and compare them with operational constraints like geofences, traffic rules and local no-go areas. Deviations - for example, vessels entering restricted zones or low, slow-moving aerial

objects near critical assets - are flagged as events with an associated threat score and explanation, and written back to the data platform as structured incident records.

Cyber-related analytics consume alerts and logs from existing IT/OT security tools, communication and GNSS-monitoring components and map them to the same event model. A correlation component then links events across domains in spatial and temporal windows, elevating the threat level when, for instance, conspicuous platform behaviour co-occurs with GNSS anomalies or cyber-security alerts.

The goal of the correlation step is produce an overall multi-domain threat level that explicitly reflects the contributing events in each domain, making the holistic assessment transparent and explainable for operators and authorities.

The chosen separation between data management, domain analytics and correlation layer, enables new sensors or detection algorithms to be integrated without modifying the overall architecture.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the conceptual framework for the DIEB project, which aims to develop a data-driven security situational awareness system for maritime critical infrastructure protection. The DIEB concept was systematically developed through structured interviews with stakeholders from MCI operators, security authorities, and regulatory bodies. These interviews identified critical capability gaps in existing multi-domain threat detection and assessment systems.

The proposed system architecture consists of three functional layers (acquisition, analysis, and communication) integrated with a central data platform. The concept emphasizes modularity, data sovereignty, explainability, and human-centred decision support. Key innovations include:

- Holistic threat assessment that correlates events across the air, water, and cyber domains
- AI methods for transparent decision support during threat assessment
- Structured communication interfaces for automated alerting and communication between MCI sites.

The DIEB concept directly addresses the capability gaps identified in Section II by providing a framework for automated, data-driven threat assessment and structured communication between MCI operators and public authorities. Therefore, the DIEB concept proposes a promising approach to enable earlier threat detection, faster response times, and improved situational awareness for maritime security stakeholders.

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